

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of DL-methionine by quinolinium fluorochromate

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The oxidation of methionine (Met) by quinolinium fluorochromate (QFC) in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) leads to the formation of corresponding sulfoxide. The reaction is of first order with respect to QFC. Michaelis-Menten type kinetics was observed with respect to methionine. The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions. The hydrogen-ion dependence has the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+]$. The oxidation of methionine was studied in nineteen different organic solvents. The solvent effect was analyzed by Kamlet's and Swain's multiparametric equations. Solvent effect indicated the importance of the cation-solvating power of the solvent. A suitable mechanism has also been postulated.

Halochromates have been used as mild and selective oxidizing reagents in synthetic organic chemistry¹. Quinolinium fluorochromate² (QFC) is also one such compound. There are, however, a few reports regarding kinetics and mechanistic aspects of QFC³ available in the literature. We have been interested in kinetics of oxidations by Cr^{VI} species and a few reports^{4,5} on oxidation by QFC have already been emanated by us. There seems to be no report on the oxidation of methionine by QFC. Methionine (Met), a sulphur-containing essential amino acid, is reported to behave differently from other amino acids, towards many oxidants⁶, due to electron-rich sulphur center which is easily oxidizable. Therefore, in continuation of our earlier work on the oxidation studies by halochromates, we report here in the kinetics of oxidation of DL-methionine by QFC in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) as solvent. A suitable mechanism has also been proposed.

Results and discussion

Stoichiometry :

The oxidation of methionine by QFC resulted in the formation of the corresponding sulfoxides. The overall reaction may therefore, be represented as eq. (1),

QFC undergoes a two-electron reduction. This accords with the earlier observation with QFC^{3,4} and structurally similar pyridinium fluorochromate (PFC)⁷.

Rate laws :

The reactions were found to be first order with respect to QFC. In individual kinetic runs, plots of $\log [\text{QFC}]$ versus time were linear ($r^2 > 0.995$). Further, it was found that the observed rate constant, k_{obs} , does not depend on the initial concentration of QFC. The order with respect to methionine was less than one (Table 1). A plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of methionine by QFC at 308 K

$10^3[\text{QFC}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	[Met] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)
1.0	0.10	4.02
1.0	0.20	6.52
1.0	0.40	9.45
1.0	0.60	11.1
1.0	0.80	12.2
1.0	1.00	13.0
1.0	1.50	14.1
1.0	3.00	15.5
2.0	0.20	7.11
4.0	0.20	6.34
6.0	0.20	6.85
8.0	0.20	6.18
1.0	0.20	6.67*

*Contained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

$1/[\text{Met}]$ was linear with an intercept on the rate ordinate. Thus Michaelis-Menten type kinetics were observed with respect to Met. This leads to the postulation of following overall mechanism (eqs. 2 and 3) and the rate law (4),

$$\text{Rate} = k_2 K [\text{Met}] [\text{QFC}] / (1 + K [\text{Met}]) \quad (4)$$

The dependence of k_{obs} on the concentration of methionine was studied at different temperatures and the values of K and k_2 were evaluated from the double reciprocal plots. The thermodynamic parameters for the complex formation and activation parameters of the disproportionation of the complexes, at 298 K, were calculated from the values of K and k_2 , respectively at different temperatures (Tables 3 and 4).

Table 2. Dependence of the reaction rate on hydrogen ion concentration

[Met] = 0.20 mol dm ⁻³	[QFC] = 0.001 mol dm ⁻³ Temp. 308 K						
[TsOH]/ mol dm ⁻³	0.10	0.30	0.50	0.80	1.00	1.50	3.00
10 ⁴ k_{obs} /s ⁻¹	8.05	11.1	14.2	17.9	21.5	28.6	35.9

Table 3. Formation constants and thermodynamic parameters of the oxidation of QFC-Met complexes

$K / (\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1})$				ΔH	ΔS	ΔG
288	298	308	318 K	(kJ mol ⁻¹)	(J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	(kJ mol ⁻¹)
4.72	3.85	3.05	2.32	-20.5 ± 0.8	-50 ± 3	5.78 ± 0.6

Table 4. Rate constants and activation parameters of the decomposition of QFC-Met complexes

10 ⁴ $k_2 / (\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1})$				ΔH	ΔS	ΔG
288	298	308	318 K	(kJ mol ⁻¹)	(J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	(kJ mol ⁻¹)
4.45	9.10	17.2	35.2	49.5 ± 0.9	-138 ± 3	90.4 ± 0.7

Induced polymerisation of acrylonitrile :

The oxidation of Met, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the rate of oxidation (Table 1). Therefore, a one-electron oxidation, giving rise to free radicals, is unlikely.

Effect of acidity :

The reaction was studied at different acidities by adding varying amount of toluene-*p*-sulphonic acid (TsOH) to the reaction mixtures. The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions (Table 2). The hydrogen-ion dependence has the form $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+]$. The values of a and b are 6.66 ± 0.16 × 10⁻⁴ s⁻¹ and 14.6 ± 0.15 × 10⁻⁴ mol⁻¹ dm³ s⁻¹ respectively ($r^2 = 0.9995$).

The observed hydrogen-ion dependence suggests that

the reaction follows two mechanistic pathways, one acid-independent and another acid-dependent. The acid-catalysis may well be attributed to a protonation of QFC as (eq. 5) to yield a protonated Cr^{VI} species which is a stronger oxidant and electrophile. Formation of a protonated Cr^{VI} species has earlier been postulated in the reactions of structurally similar PFC⁷.

Solvent effect :

The oxidation of Met was studied in nineteen organic solvents. The choice of solvents was limited due to the solubility of QFC and its reaction with primary and secondary alcohols. There was no reaction with the chosen solvents. The kinetics are similar in all the solvents. The values of K and k_2 are recorded in Table 5. A perusal of the data shows

Table 5. Effect of solvents on the oxidation of methionine by QFC at 308 K

Solvents	K	10 ⁵ k_2	Solvents	K	10 ⁵ k_2
	(dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹)	(s ⁻¹)		(dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹)	(s ⁻¹)
Chloroform	4.12	63.1	Toluene	4.72	14.8
1,2-Dichloroethane	4.67	67.6	Acetophenone	5.38	70.8
Dichloromethane	4.61	58.9	THF	5.45	24.5
DMSO	3.05	172	<i>t</i> -Butylalcohol	4.65	35.5
Acetone	4.86	50.1	1,4-Dioxane	3.95	26.3
DMF	5.67	95.5	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	5.50	16.9
Butanone	4.36	37.2	CS ₂	4.45	8.71
Nitrobenzene	3.78	75.9	Acetic acid	5.28	41.7
Benzene	4.16	17.8	Ethyl acetate	4.81	21.4
Cyclohexane	4.55	2.45			

that the formation constants do not vary much with the nature of the solvents. However, the rate constants, k_2 varied considerably with the solvents. The rate constants for oxidation, k_2 , in eighteen solvents (CS₂ was not considered, as the complete range of the solvent parameters was not available) were correlated in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship eq. (6) of Kamlet *et al.*⁸.

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + a\alpha \quad (6)$$

In this equation, π^* represents the solvent polarity, β the hydrogen bond acceptor basicities and α is the hydrogen bond donor acidity. A_0 is the intercept term. It may be mentioned here that out of the 18 solvents, 12 have a value of zero for α . The results of correlation analyses in terms of eq. (6), a biparametric equation involving π^* and β , and

separately with π^* and β are given below.

$$\log k_2 = -4.47 + 1.52 (\pm 0.19)\pi^* + 0.21 (\pm 0.16)\beta^* - 0.12 (\pm 0.15)\alpha \quad (7)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8422; sd = 0.18; n = 18; \psi = 0.44$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.50 + 1.47 (\pm 0.18)\pi^* + 0.25 (\pm 0.15)\beta \quad (8)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8352; sd = 0.17; n = 18; \psi = 0.43$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.50 + 1.54 (\pm 0.19)\pi^* \quad (9)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8057; sd = 0.19; n = 18; \psi = 0.45$$

$$\log k_2 = -3.64 + 0.59 (\pm 0.33)\beta \quad (10)$$

$$r^2 = 0.1323; sd = 0.39; n = 18; \psi = 0.96$$

Here n is the number of data points and ψ is the Exner's statistical parameter⁹.

Kamlet's⁸ triparametric equation explains *ca.* 84% of the effect of solvent on the oxidation. However, by Exner's⁹ criterion the correlation is not even satisfactory (*cf.* eq. 7). The major contribution is of solvent polarity. It alone accounted for *ca.* 81% of the data. Both β and α play relatively minor roles.

The data on the solvent effect were analysed in terms of Swain's equation¹⁰ of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents as well.

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (11)$$

Here A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and B the cation-solvating power. C is the intercept term. $(A + B)$ is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of eq. (11), separately with A and B and with $(A + B)$.

$$\log k_2 = 1.28 (\pm 0.03)A + 1.29 (\pm 0.02)B - 3.75 \quad (12)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9963; sd = 0.03; n = 19; \psi = 0.06$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.08 (\pm 0.47)A - 2.78 \quad (13)$$

$$r^2 = 0.2359; sd = 0.38; n = 19; \psi = 0.90$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.32 (\pm 0.23)B - 3.34 \quad (14)$$

$$r^2 = 0.6669; sd = 0.25; n = 19; \psi = 0.59$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.37 \pm 0.03 (A + B) - 3.75 \quad (15)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9933; sd = 0.04; n = 19; \psi = 0.08$$

The rates of oxidation of methionine in different solvents show an excellent correlation with Swain's equation with both the cation- and anion-solvating powers playing significant roles, though the contribution of the cation-solvation is slightly more than that of the anion-solvation. The solvent polarity, represented by $(A + B)$, also accounted for *ca.* 99% of the data. However, the correlations individually

with A and B were poor. In view of the fact that solvent polarity is able to account for *ca.* 99% of the data, an attempt was made to correlate the rate with the relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of the relative permittivity is not linear ($r^2 = 0.5066$; $sd = 0.30$; $\psi = 0.72$).

The observed solvent effect points to a transition state more polar than the reactant state. Further, the formation of a dipolar transition state, similar to those of S_N2 reactions, is indicated by the major role of both anion- and cation-solvating powers. However, the solvent effect may also be explained assuming that the oxidant and the intermediate complex exist as ion-pair in non-polar solvent like cyclohexane and be considerably dissociated in more polar solvents.

Mechanism :

In view of the absence of any effect of radical scavenger, acrylonitrile, on the reaction rate, it is unlikely that a one-electron oxidation giving rise to free radicals, is operative in this oxidation reaction. The experimental results can be accounted for in terms of electrophilic oxygen transfer from QFC to the methionine-sulphur via an intermediate complex (eq. 16). Similar mechanisms has been suggested for oxidation of sulfides and iodide ions by periodate ion¹¹ and for the oxidation of sulfides by hydrogen peroxide¹² and PFC¹³. The electrophilic attack on the sulphide-sulphur can be viewed as an S_N2 reaction. An S_N2 like

Scheme 1

transition state is supported by observed solvent effect also.

The oxidation of methionine by QFC may involve a cyclic intermediate as has been suggested in many reactions of Cr^{VI}¹⁴. The cyclic transition state will be highly strained in view of the apical position of a lone pair of electrons or an alkyl group (eq. 17). The formation of a cyclic transition state entails a more exacting specificity of orientation and should result in much larger negative entropy of activation than that observed.

It is of interest to compare here the mode of oxidation of methionine by PFC¹⁵, pyridinium chlorochromate (PCC)¹⁶, pyridinium bromochromate (PBC)¹⁷ and QFC. The oxidation by PFC and PBC presented a similar kinetic picture, i.e. the reactions are of first-order with respect to the reductants. While in the oxidation by PCC and QFC, Michaelis-Menten type kinetics was observed with respect to the reductants. It is possible that the values of the formation constants for the reductant-PFC/PBC complexes are very low. This resulted in the observation of second-order kinetics. No explanation of the difference is available presently. Solvent effects and the dependence of the hydrogen ions are of similar nature in all these reactions, for which essentially similar mechanisms have been proposed.

Experimental

Materials :

QFC was prepared by the reported method² and its purity checked by an iodometric method. Methionine (Merck) was used as supplied. Due to non-aqueous nature of the solvent, toluene-*p*-sulphonic acid (TsOH) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. Other solvents were purified by the usual methods¹⁸.

Product analysis :

Product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions. The oxidation of Met by QFC resulted in the formation of corresponding sulphoxide, which was determined by the reported method¹⁹. The yield of sulphoxide was 94 ± 3%. The oxidation state of chromium in completely reduced reaction mixtures i.e. after >10 half-lives, as determined iodometrically, was +4.

Kinetic measurements :

The pseudo-first order conditions were attained by maintaining a large excess (× 15 or more) of the Met over QFC. The solvent was DMSO, unless specified otherwise. The reactions were followed, at constant temperatures (±0.1 K), by monitoring the decrease in [QFC] spectrophotometrically at 365 nm. No other reactant or product has any significant

absorption at this wavelength. The pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , was evaluated from the linear ($r = 0.990-0.999$) plots of $\log [QFC]$ against time for up to 80% reaction. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within ±3%. All experiments, other than those for studying the effect of hydrogen ions, were carried out in the absence of TsOH.

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